

RI4C2
Research & Innovation
For Cities & Citizens

This project has received funding from
the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and
innovation programme under grant agreement No
101035803

D4.5 Knowledge Ecosystem Database

Technical delivery

DELIVERABLE 4.5
MONTH 13

D4.5 Knowledge Ecosystem Database

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I. The database

A Knowledge Ecosystem consists of users and producers of knowledge, organized around joint knowledge search.

The EC2U Knowledge Ecosystem Dataset is the result of the survey conducted by WP6 to map the Local Knowledge Ecosystems as key actors involved in Research and Innovation processes.

The database is aimed at mapping all the actors within the consortium in order to facilitate partnership and knowledge sharing, research projects and applications.

The mapping of the Citizen science initiatives, also included in the dataset, aims to deliver the prizes for Citizen Science Champions, a delivery of WP6.

Both the survey and the dataset will be open all along the project to collect new entries that will be displayed by the Knowledge Ecosystem Database and publicly available (according to the permission delivered by the data owner).

II. Data Access

The database is accessible at the following link:

<https://tinyurl.com/24f693ej>

An example of an available interface for research and analysis of the data is available at:

<https://tinyurl.com/2yaztqtl>

The main link will be available also via the Database Directory page on the EC2U project website (tool under development).

III. Data model

The survey maps the actors according to the following list:

- **Universities and Research entities** (e.g. Universities/University Alliances/University Associations, Research Institutes/Researchers communities/Public research institutions, Research Camps, Industrial parks, Research Centres/Hubs or Think Tanks, Research clusters/platforms, Research Departments in companies)
- **Innovative start-ups** (e.g. Innovation Associations/Programs, Bootcamps, Entrepreneurs, Unicorns, Spin-offs)
- **Local and regional authorities** (e.g. Local and Regional Public Administration Authorities, County councils, representatives of municipalities, local governmental bodies; public institutions; social assistance services, local authorities for social protection and rights, Public health authorities)

- **Venture capital, sponsors** (e.g. Local and Regional funding/investing agencies, Consulting companies and agencies, Start-up Nation program Investment groups, business solution groups, tech investors, private equity firms)
- **Service organizations** (e.g. non-governmental organizations, Associations of patients, Local and regional communities (neighbourhood associations), Professional associations, Students' associations and organisations, vendors, intermediaries, any other support entities)
- **Incumbent firms** (e.g. existing companies as users of research and innovation results: local and regional enterprises, companies and corporations)
- **Citizen Science entities** (e.g. European Citizen Science Association; Local or regional Citizen Sciences Entities, citizen scientists)
- **Others.**

The main areas of the activities and projects carried out by the entities are classified according to the following taxonomy:

- Agriculture, forestry and rural areas
- Bioeconomy
- Energy
- Environment
- Food systems
- Frontier research
- Health
- Industry
- Information and communication technologies
- Oceans and seas
- Security
- Small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs)
- Social sciences and humanities
- Space
- Synergies with structural funds
- Transport
- Others

The level of involvement in R&I activities is classified as:

- At local level
- At regional level
- At national level
- At international level

IV. Licensing

The EC2U Knowledge Ecosystems Dataset is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution-Non Commercial-No Derivatives 4.0 International, according to the general licensing policies specified in the RI4C2 M12 D4.2 Data Dissemination Definition deliverable.

V. Use cases

The existing dataset is fully searchable crossing all the criteria (see Fig. 1)

Fig. 1

The tool allows also to visualize data using data visualization formats (see Fig. 2 and Fig. 3).

Fig. 2

Fig. 3

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